

Effect of organic solvents and concentration on electrochemical reduction behaviour of *N,N'*-(di-benzylidene)-*p*-phenylenediamine

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Abstract : The electrochemical reduction behaviour of *N,N'*-(di-benzylidene)-*p*-phenylenediamine in 1 : 1 aquo-organic mixtures of different organic solvents, in the pH range from 2.0 to 12.0 at 30 °C and the effect of concentration in the same pH range at various concentrations from 0.2 to 1.0 mM have been studied. The diffusion current (i_d), diffusion current coefficient (D) values are found to decrease and half-wave potentials ($E_{1/2}$) shift to more negative values. The heterogeneous forward rate constant ($k_{f,h}^0$) values are found to decrease, whereas the activation free energy change (ΔG) values are increases in the presence of organic solvents.

Keywords : Electrochemical, diffusion, potential, solvent.

In continuation of our earlier report¹, an attempt has been made to study the electrochemical reduction behaviour of *N,N'*-(di-benzylidene)-*p*-phenylenediamine in presence of 1 : 1 aquo-organic mixtures of different organic solvents, viz. methanol, ethanol, *n*-propanol, dimethylsulfoxide, dimethylformamide and ethyleneglycol, in the pH range from 7.48 to 12.0 and effect of concentration in the same pH range. The diffusion coefficient (D), diffusion current constant (I) and radius (r) are determined to throw some light on the size of the reduced species of di-Schiff base and also $k_{f,h}^0$; ΔG and α_{n_a} values are evaluated to study the irreversibility of the reduction process.

Results and discussion

Effect of organic solvents : The diffusion current (i_d) is found to decrease remarkably in the presence of organic solvents. The decreasing order of diffusion current is, aqueous > methanol > ethanol > dimethylformamide > *n*-propanol > dimethylsulfoxide > ethyleneglycol. The decrease in diffusion current (i_d) may be ascribed to decrease in effective diffusion coefficient (D). The diffusion coefficient (D) for the depolarizer solutions in the absence and presence of organic solvents are calculated using eqs. (1) and (2) respectively. The decrease in diffusion coefficient (D) may be due to either the increase in viscosity of the solution or the change in the size of the solvated species (r)². It may be difficult for the quantitative interpretation of separate influence of these two effects whether they reinforce or compensate each other.

$$D = \frac{3.38 \times 10^{-5}}{(V_m)^{1/3} \eta} \quad (1)$$

In which V_m is apparent molar volume and η is viscosity of the solution

$$\frac{\eta_{\text{aq}}^{1/2}}{\eta_{\text{org}}^{1/2}} = \frac{D_{\text{org}}^{1/2}}{D_{\text{aq}}^{1/2}} \quad (2)$$

The extent of decrease in diffusion current depends on the nature of the organic solvents and to the increase in the viscosity (η) of solvents. It is evident from the Ilkovic equation that the diffusion current is inversely proportional to the viscosity (η). The nearly constant values of $i_d \eta^{1/2}$ reveals that the increase in square root of viscosity is compensated by the decrease in diffusion current. The diffusion current constant (I) values in different organic solvents are evaluated using the eq. (3) and they are found to follow the same decreasing order as that of the diffusion current (i_d). The decrease in the diffusion current constant (I) may be due to an increase in the size of diffusing species³⁻⁵ or may be due to increase in ionic interactions⁶.

$$I = \frac{i_d}{C.m^{2/3}.t^{1/6}} \quad (3)$$

where C is concentration of the depolarizer (mM/L), m is flow rate (mg/s) and t is drop time (s).

The diffusion-controlled nature of the polarograms of

Table 1. Effect of 1 : 1 aquo-organic mixtures of different organic solvents on electrochemical reduction of *N,N'*-(di-benzylidene)-*p*-phenylenediamine at pH 8.95 and 10.46

Solvent	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	i_d (μA)	αn_a	$i_d \eta^{1/2}$	I	$D \times 10^6$ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	r (A)	$k_{1h}^0 \times 10^{21}$ ($\text{cm} \text{s}^{-1}$)	ΔG (kcal mol^{-1})
pH = 8.95									
Aqueous	1.490	9.35	0.797	5.895	7.21	3.986	1.43	20.75	34.36
Methanol	1.498	7.18	0.778	5.744	5.53	3.662	1.50	3.190	56.09
Ethanol	1.502	6.31	0.781	6.607	4.86	2.553	1.92	2.587	56.63
<i>n</i> -Propanol	1.518	5.01	0.784	6.568	3.86	2.312	1.94	1.174	57.53
Dimethylsulfoxide	1.511	4.75	0.795	6.750	3.66	1.903	1.84	7.697	57.92
Dimethylformamide	1.535	5.62	0.786	6.450	4.33	2.446	2.00	6.566	57.70
Ethyleneglycol	1.495	4.10	0.792	5.970	3.16	1.790	2.35	7.403	57.67
pH = 10.46									
Aqueous	1.520	7.30	0.784	3.972	5.63	3.164	0.73	15.34	34.55
Methanol	1.542	5.01	0.766	4.008	3.86	2.832	1.13	1.762	56.45
Ethanol	1.537	4.12	0.770	4.314	3.18	1.921	1.31	1.397	57.01
<i>n</i> -Propanol	1.555	3.21	0.776	4.208	2.47	1.727	1.18	1.081	57.95
Dimethylsulfoxide	1.549	2.94	0.781	4.178	2.27	1.426	1.20	6.380	58.19
Dimethylformamide	1.563	3.85	0.772	4.439	2.97	1.893	1.06	5.742	57.97
Ethyleneglycol	1.530	2.53	0.779	3.684	1.95	1.232	1.55	6.121	57.72

N,N'-(di-benzylidene)-*p*-phenylenediamine in presence of various organic solvents is evident from the plots of i_d vs $h^{1/2}$, which are linear and passing through the origin. The half-wave potentials ($E_{1/2}$) shift to more negative values in the presence of organic solvents and they follow the order : dimethylformamide > *n*-propanol > dimethylsulfoxide > ethanol > methanol > ethyleneglycol > aqueous. The increase in $E_{1/2}$ values may be attributed to several factors such as dielectric constant (ϵ), solvation of ions and adsorption of organic solvent molecules at the electrode surface. The variation of $E_{1/2}$ values with dielectric constant (ϵ) is given by Takahashi relation (4)⁷.

$$E_{1/2(s)} = E_{1/2(w)} - k \left[\frac{1}{\epsilon_{(w)}} + \frac{1}{\epsilon_{(s)}} \right] \quad (4)$$

In which $E_{1/2(w)}$ and $E_{1/2(s)}$ are half-wave potentials in aqueous and aquo-organic mixtures respectively and k is a constant. The plots $E_{1/2(s)}$ vs $(1/\epsilon_{(s)})$, which are linear indicates the shift in $E_{1/2(s)}$ is a linear function of $1/\epsilon_{(s)}$. This indicates that dielectric constant is a dominant factor in the present study. However, the shift in $E_{1/2}$ values to more negative values may also be due to adsorption of organic molecules to some extent at the electrode surface. This accumulation of organic solvent molecules retards

Table 2. Effect of concentration on electrochemical reduction of *N,N'*-(di-benzylidene)-*p*-phenylenediamine at different pH values

Concn. (mM/L)	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	i_d (μA)	i_d/c	D ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	αn_a	$-E_{1/2}$ (V)	i_d (μA)	i_d/c	D ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	αn_a
pH = 7.48					pH = 8.95					
0.2	1.312	1.98	9.75	4.893	0.745	1.461	1.89	9.45	3.980	0.738
0.4	1.365	3.95	9.88	5.274	0.751	1.466	3.75	9.38	4.325	0.747
0.6	1.409	5.87	9.78	5.583	0.772	1.472	5.57	9.28	4.482	0.768
0.8	1.434	7.58	9.48	5.725	0.780	1.481	7.45	9.31	4.693	0.781
1.0	1.465	9.86	9.86	5.986	0.807	1.490	9.35	9.35	4.915	0.797
pH = 9.51					pH = 10.46					
0.2	1.461	1.76	8.80	3.865	0.732	1.489	1.51	7.55	3.164	0.723
0.4	1.469	3.43	8.58	3.865	0.748	1.495	2.89	7.23	3.451	0.736
0.6	1.475	5.02	8.37	4.103	0.763	1.503	4.76	7.93	3.665	0.760
0.8	1.482	6.76	8.45	4.386	0.776	1.511	5.82	7.28	3.821	0.772
1.0	1.500	8.43	8.43	4.592	0.791	1.520	7.30	7.30	4.043	0.790

the adsorption of depolariser species at the electrode surface. Thus the reduction of depolariser requires higher energy and hence half-wave potentials ($E_{1/2}$) shifts to more negative values.

The heterogeneous formal rate constant ($k_{f,h}^o$) and the activation free energy change (ΔG) values are calculated using Meities-Israel⁸ method. In absence of organic solvents at pH 8.95 and 10.46, the $k_{f,h}^o$ values are found to be 20.75×10^{-21} and 15.34×10^{-21} cm s⁻¹ and ΔG values are 34.36 and 34.55 kcal mol⁻¹ respectively. These $k_{f,h}^o$ values are found to decrease in the presence of organic solvents indicating that irreversibility of reduction process increases. It is further supported by the increase in the ΔG values. The high value of ΔG indicate that transition state is highly solvated⁹. The $k_{f,h}^o$ values decreases with the increase in the chain length of aliphatic alcohols. This may be due to the increase in the size of solvated species of depolariser at the electrode surface, which leads to decrease in the diffusion coefficient values. The little increase in ΔG values with higher aliphatic alcohols indicates the increased destabilization of alcohols, which is expected from the positive inductive effect of the alkyl groups present in aliphatic alcohols¹⁰.

$$E_{d,e} = E_{1/2} - \frac{0.055}{\alpha n_a} \log \frac{i}{(i_d - i)} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{where, } E_{1/2} = -0.2412 \cdot \frac{0.0615}{\alpha n_a} \log \frac{1.349 k_{f,h}^o t^{1/2}}{D^{1/2}} \quad (6)$$

$$k_{f,h}^o = \frac{kT}{h} r_o \exp - (\Delta G / RT) \quad (7)$$

The αn_a (where α is transfer coefficient and n_a is no. of electrons involved in rate determining step) values derived in the presence of organic solvents found to decrease when they are compare with the values obtained in the absence of organic solvents. The α values obtained from the αn_a values in presence of organic solvents, reveals that the reduction process is irreversible. The decrease in αn_a values compare to the values obtained in absence of organic solvents, attribute to sole decrease in the value of α but not to the value of n_a , which indicates the irreversibility of reduction process increase in presence of organic solvents. This indicates that electroreduction mechanism of *N,N'*-(di-benzylidene)-*p*-phenylenediamine is same even in the presence of organic solvents as in the absence of organic solvents, although the diffusion current values decreases remarkably and half-wave potentials ($E_{1/2}$) shift to more negative values.

Effect of concentration : The effect of change in concentration of *N,N'*-(di-benzylidene)-*p*-phenylenediamine on electrochemical reduction behaviour has been studied in the pH range from 7.48 to 12.0 at constant temperature of 30 °C. In this study, the concentration varies from 0.2 to 1.0 milli moles/lit (mM/L) at all pH values studied.

The diffusion current (i_d) is dependent on the concentration of the depolariser. This behaviour clearly indicates the irreversible nature of the polarograms. The irreversibility of reduction process is further confirmed by the slopes of log plots ($-E_{d,c}$ vs $\log [i/(i_d - i)]$) (Table 2). The increase in the αn_a values is due to increase in the value of α , which reveals that irreversibility of reduction process decreases with the concentration. The increase in diffusion current (i_d) values with the concentration is ascribed to increase in diffusion coefficient value¹¹. The plots i_d vs concentration, which are linear and passing through the origin, indicating the diffusion-controlled nature of the polarograms. The constancy of i_d/c values shows the validity of quantitative analysis of the di-Schiff base by using polarographic method. This is also useful to determine the validity of the Ilkovic equation. The half-wave potentials ($E_{1/2}$) shift to more negative values with the concentration. This may be ascribed to the factors that the increase in dissociation constant of pre-protonated species and decrease in surface concentration at the electrode. The adsorbability of the depolarizer at the electrode surface decreases due to increase in ionic interactions with concentration and hence, surface concentration decreases at the electrode surface. Obviously, the decreased surface concentration would retards the electrode reaction, thereby $E_{1/2}$ shift to more negative values¹³.

The electrode process is accompanied by pre-protonation and the increase in dissociation constant of pre-protonated species^{12,13}. This factor sharply lower the rate of pre-protonation and consequently lead to the shift in $E_{1/2}$ values to more negative values.

Experimental

The *N,N'*-(di-benzylidene)-*p*-phenylenediamine compound was prepared from phenylenediamine (Sisco, India) and benzaldehyde (Sisco, India) of A.R. grade, according to reported method¹⁴. The organic solvents

except dimethylsulfoxide, dimethylformamide and ethyleneglycol were purified according to the methods reported¹⁵. These three organic solvents were used as supplied by Sisco, India. The dissolved oxygen from solutions of depolarizer was removed by passing nitrogen gas for about 20 min. The ionic strength was maintained by the addition of required amount of KCl. To suppress the polarographic maxima. Triton-X 100 ($5 \times 10^{-4}\%$) was used. The dropping mercury electrode was having characteristics of $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.39 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$, was used as a working electrode and SCE as reference electrode. The polarograms were recorded at 30 ± 0.1 °C on polarograph model CL02 in conjunction with polyflex galvanometer model PL50 supplied by Thoshniwal Instruments, Bombay. The pH meter was a digital model DL-707, supplied by Digisun Electronics, Hyderabad. The viscosity of the solutions was measured with the Ostwald's viscometer and the values obtained were comparable with the reported values.

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